

PROCESS SIMULATION MODELS FOR FILAMENT WINDING TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to set and review the development of mathematical models that simulate the main phenomena that occurs during the winding and curing process of filament winding technology.

The studied models provide the wound composite temperature, degree of cure, viscosity, fiber position and fiber tension as a function of position and time during filament winding and subsequent cure.

Particular attention was paid to the use of an appropriate rheological model: a combination of the Williams-Landel-Ferry model with a semi-empirical model was used to describe the behaviour of commercial epoxy resin systems.

Moreover, the residual stresses and strains within the wound composite during and after curing can be calculated.

Keywords: Filament Winding, Modelling and Simulation, Curing Process.

1. INTRODUCTION

General software packages have been developed for the numerical simulation of geodesic and non-geodesic winding paths with regard to axi-symmetric and non axi-symmetric bodies [1,2,3]. However, the fabrication of wound composites is still based mainly on a trial and error procedure, because numerical simulation has not yet been applied to the development of control systems which can correlate the main parameters of the winding and curing processes with the processing behaviour and the final properties of the component. Understanding of this processing-structure-properties relationship and its implementation in industrial manufacturing procedures, is the starting point to guarantee the high quality and reliability required for mass production.

2. MODELLING OF THE CURING PROCESS

Processing of thermosetting matrix composite materials by filament winding is achieved by winding a fiber tape impregnated with resin around a mandrel. Fiber impregnation can occur immediately before the winding process, conveying the fiber through a resin bath (wet winding). Alternatively a commercial pre-impregnated fiber tape can be used. This second possibility offers a cleaner and less toxic, but more expensive, process than the first one. From the point of view of the curing model the same equations can describe both processes.

Generally, the process is performed at room temperature. However, depending on the specific resin system utilized, the mandrel can be heated or cooled. The mandrel temperature will

Figure 1 - Sketch of the mandrel-composite cylindrical assembly.

be represented by T_m . For all cases, once the composite is formed the system is heated to promote and complete the matrix polymerization reactions. The external temperature to which the composite is subjected will be represented by T_c . Applying hydrostatic pressure $p(t)$ during the cure process promotes composite consolidation, avoiding the formation of gas bubbles during resin reaction.

A geometric representation of the composite forming process is shown in Fig. 1, where the main dimensional parameters and boundary conditions are indicated. For the sake of simplicity, in the present analysis a circular section of the composite, with uniform thickness in the z and ϑ directions, will be considered. The thickness is allowed to vary with time during winding, as new layers are added, and during post-cure, as a consequence of composite shrinkage. Moreover, the thickness of the composite cylinder is assumed to be much smaller than the length. Thermal and mechanical effects associated with the composite ends are neglected, and only transfer phenomena along the r direction are considered.

Modelling a technological process means describing, through mathematical equations, the phenomena that occur during the process. Usually, achieving such an objective requires mass balance, force balance and energy balance equations. The strongly non-linear character of the resulting system may be reduced by decoupling some of the phenomena and dependent variables into sub-models. This method has been followed by many authors in the past [4,5,6].

Our case objective is the development of relationships between the thermo-chemical properties of the resin-fiber system and the controlled processing parameters (fiber angle and tension, winding speed, heating rate, cure temperature and time). In particular, the following variables will be described as a function of time and radial position: mandrel and composite temperature; degree of cure of the resin; resin viscosity; fiber position; fiber tension; stress and strain on the mandrel-composite cylinder; mechanical properties of the final composite part.

In order to achieve the proposed goal, development of different sub-models to consider the balance equations of the complex physical and chemical phenomena that occur during the process is necessary.

This analysis subdivides the process into four sub-models:

1. fiber motion sub-model;
2. thermal sub-model;
3. kinetic and rheological sub-model;
4. stress-strain sub-model.

As shown in Fig. 2, integration of these sub-models constitutes the filament winding process master model. Fig. 2 also shows the specific input and output parameters, process variables

and the interrelation between these sub-models [7].

Figure 2 - Scheme of the sub-models interconnection.

3. FIBER MOTION SUB-MODEL

Considering the balance of the forces acting on the fibers at each layer, this sub-model computes the position, displacement and instantaneous tension of the fibers, the thickness of each layer and the whole composite plus the fiber volume fraction. Input data for this sub-model are the physical and mechanical properties of the raw materials, the geometrical dimensions of the mandrel and the composite, and processing parameters such as winding angle and tension. Other data including actual temperature, degree of polymerization and viscosity of the resin are provided by other sub-models.

The fiber tension radial component produces a radial displacement $w_f^{(j)}$, where the index j indicates the j -th layer of the composite. After reaching the resin gel point the fibers are blocked in their position and no more displacements are allowed.

Temperature changes in the cylinder, and the consequent variation in the degree of cure of the resin, produce expansions and contractions of the system, with a radial component u_{TS} that is computed in the stress-strain sub-model.

The radial displacement $w_f^{(j)}$ depends on the balance between the fiber tension radial component and the resistance that the viscous resin presents to fiber movement [4]. Radial tension is a function of the fiber modulus E_f , whereas the viscous resistance follows Darcy's law of flows through porous media and is a function of the permeability S of the fibers. Considering these two contributions, the displacement of a fiber layer during a short time interval dt is given by the following expression:

$$\Delta w_f^{(j)} = -\frac{S \cdot \sigma_f^{(j)}}{\mu^{(j)} r_f^{(j)}} \Delta t \sin^2 \phi^{(j)} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) $\mu^{(j)}$ is the resin viscosity, $r_f^{(j)}$ is the radial coordinate indicating the position of the considered j -th layer and $\sigma_f^{(j)}$ the stress in the fiber due to the winding force F . Evidently, the effective force F on the fiber is continuously changing from its initial value F_0 as the winding proceeds [7].

An example of computation of fiber layer displacement as a function of time during the whole process [7] is given in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 - Radial position of the layers.

4. THERMAL SUB-MODEL

This sub-model, based on the solution of the energy balance, will provide the distribution of temperature through the cylinder radius as a function of time. Input data are the raw material thermal properties and thermal boundary conditions. The geometry and the instantaneous position of the fibers are given by the fiber motion sub-model, whereas the reaction kinetic responsible for the heat developed by the polymerization process, is given by the kinetic sub-model. The main contributions to temperature variations are due to the heat developed during

the polymerization reaction H_r , and by heat diffusion in the radial direction. These quantities are reflected in the energy balance equation, that for the adopted cylindrical geometry is written in the following form:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r K_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \rho H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (2)$$

ρ , C and K_r are, respectively, instantaneous density, specific heat and thermal conductivity of the composite; H_r is total reaction heat. α is the degree of cure, defined as a function of the heat developed instantaneously from the start of the reaction:

$$\alpha(t) = H(t)/H_r \quad (3)$$

The Eq. 2 reveals that an expression for the reaction rate is needed:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = f_1(\alpha, t) \quad (4)$$

The development of appropriate models for the reaction rate will be discussed in the kinetic sub-model section. Moreover, an appropriate model of the composite properties (ρ , C , K_r), as a function of fiber volume fraction, temperature and degree of polymerization must also be provided [7].

To complete the model, the initial and boundary conditions have to be imposed:

$$\begin{cases} T = T_0^{(j)} \\ \alpha = \alpha_0^{(j)} \end{cases} \quad \text{for} \quad t = t_0^{(j)} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{cases} T = T_m \\ T = T_c \end{cases} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{for} \quad r = r_{mi} \\ \text{for} \quad r = r_{mo} + h(t) \end{array} \quad (6)$$

Finite differences have been applied to solve the parabolic differential Eq. 2.

Fig. 4 shows an example [7], based on this model, of computation of the temperature distribution.

5. KINETIC AND RHEOLOGICAL SUB-MODEL

This model provides polymerization rate, degree of cure, heat of reaction and viscosity of the resin as a function of position and time. The input data are the parameters of the kinetic and rheological equations that are obtained during the experimental characterization program.

The composite geometry and the instantaneous position of the fibers are given by the fiber motion submodel, whereas the temperature distribution is given by the thermal sub-model. In this study, reactive epoxy resins will be considered as they constitute the most widely used matrixes for advanced composites. Two main systems are normally used: Tetraglycidil-diamindiphenylmethane (TGDDM) cured with Diamindiphenylsulphone (DDS) and Diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) cured with Diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM). TGDDM has four epoxy reactive groups. For this reason it produces denser and stronger networks than the DGEBA molecule, which has only two epoxy reactive groups. This difference is evinced in the different maximum glass transition temperature reached by both materials (TGDDM: $T_{g\infty} = 200$ °C, DGEBA: $T_{g\infty} = 160$ °C).

Several kinetic models have been developed to describe polymerization of the epoxy matrixes [4,5,8]. Considering that the exact chemical composition of the resins is generally unknown, for commercial systems only empirical models can be used. Although the reported behaviour of different epoxy based systems have been reviewed in this research, only two specific systems will be considered here. In particular two commercial Ciba-Geigy products (Araldite

Figure 4 - Temperature throughout the process within the mandrel-composite cylinder.

LY-564 cured with HY-2954, hardener, and Araldite LY-556 cured with HY-2918, anhydride, and DY-070, accelerant) were characterized by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The characterization method, which is described in detail elsewhere, included 5 isothermal tests performed at different temperatures in the range of the normal processing temperature and 3 dynamic tests performed at 3 heating rates [9]. Test results, expressed in terms of degree of cure, according to Eq. (4), were processed by multiple non-linear regression analysis. The following kinetic model was found to describe the kinetic behaviour of these systems:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt}(T, \alpha) = (K_1 + K_2\alpha^m)(\alpha_m - \alpha)^n \quad (7)$$

where α_m , the maximum degree of cure obtained at lower temperatures, is a linear function of T :

$$\alpha_m = p + qT \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (7) m and n are reaction orders and K_1 and K_2 kinetic constants depending on temperature through an Arrhenius type expression:

$$K_i = A_i \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E_i}{RT}\right) \quad (9)$$

The parameters of Eqs. (7), (8) and (9) are reported in the following table:

	Araldite LY-564	Araldite LY-556
A_1 (s^{-1})	$1.08 \cdot 10^6$	$4.26 \cdot 10^4$
A_2 (s^{-1})	$1.16 \cdot 10^5$	$3.07 \cdot 10^5$
ΔE_1 (J/mol)	$7.176 \cdot 10^4$	$6.138 \cdot 10^4$
ΔE_2 (J/mol)	$5.386 \cdot 10^4$	$6.212 \cdot 10^4$
m	0.56	0.64
n	1.44	1.36
p	0.6037	-1.434
q	$8.73 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.91 \cdot 10^{-3}$
H_r (J/kg)	427000.	365000.

Table 1 - Parameters for the kinetic model of Araldite LY-564 and Araldite LY-556.

An experimental verification of the model predictions for isothermal (Fig. 5) and dynamic (Fig. 6.a) test conditions has given excellent results [9].

Figure 5 - Comparison between experimental and numerical results for the degree of cure of the Araldite LY-556 resin system under isothermal conditions.

With respect to the rheological behaviour of these reactive systems, two main contributions must be considered. The first one is associated with the molecular mobility changes as a consequence of temperature variations (physical effect); the second one is related to the molecular structural changes induced by the cure reaction (chemical effect). Several theoretical and empirical models have been reported in scientific literature. Again, only empirical models were considered in this work as useful tools to describe the rheological behaviour of commercial systems with unknown composition. The characterization of the studied epoxy system was performed using a parallel plates rheometer with the same test conditions used during the kinetic characterization. Mobility changes due to temperature effect were modelled following the well-known William, Landel and Ferry (WLF) equation, whereas chemical effects due to the growing molecular structure were modelled using an empirical term which predicts infinite viscosity at the gel point (α_g) [9]. The full rheological model is represented by the following expression:

$$\mu(T, \alpha) = \mu_g \exp \left[\frac{C_1(T - T_g(\alpha))}{C_2 + T - T_g(\alpha)} \right] \left(\frac{\alpha_g}{\alpha_g - \alpha} \right)^n \quad (10)$$

where μ_g is the viscosity at the glassy state, C_1 and C_2 are the constants of the WLF equation, n is an empirical exponent and $T_g(\alpha)$ is the continuously changing glass transition temperature of the reactive system. The following dependence for T_g as a function of α was obtained:

$$T_g(\alpha) = a + b\alpha + c\alpha^2 \quad (11)$$

The parameter values of the full rheological model represented by Eqs. (10) and (11) are given in the following table:

	Araldite LY-564	Araldite LY-556
μ_0 (Pa · s)	10^{12}	10^{12}
C_1	35.56	35.87
C_2 (K)	22.56	17.99
n	2.01	1.98
a	236.01	235.36
b	117.14	38.225
c	0	142.58
α_g	0.64	0.331

Table 2 - Parameters for the rheological model of Araldite LY-564 and Araldite LY-556.

Some relevant results [9], concerning the experimental verification of the rheological model, are shown in Fig. 6.b.

Figure 6 - Comparison between experimental and numerical results for a) degree of cure under dynamical conditions and b) viscosity under isothermal conditions of the Araldite LY-556 resin system.

6. STRESS-STRAIN SUB-MODEL

The stress-strain sub-model gives the distribution of stresses and strains at the layer interphases as a function of time. Input data required for this computation are the mechanical properties, the thermal expansion coefficients and the chemical shrinkage coefficients of the materials. This sub-model uses the geometrical distribution of the layers and the temperature and degree of polymerization distribution through the composite thickness provided respectively by the fiber motion, thermal and kinetic sub-models. The stress-strain sub-model gives separately the stress state due to the initial winding tension and the stress due to thermal and chemical effects. In Fig. 7 the calculated stresses due to the winding tension for a ten layer winding are shown [7].

7. CONCLUSION

The study of a master model for filament winding technology and its implementation in a simulation code has been presented. The practical utilization of the four described sub-models requires the solution of a system of coupled differential equations describing the different phenomena. This solution can be obtained by applying numerical techniques. Some relevant results giving an idea of the potential of the simulation code are reported in this paper. The research program includes a test activity for experimental validation of the models. This part of the work is in progress and will be completed in the near future.

Figure 7 - Normal stress σ_r due to the winding tension.

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